

SECTION 17

HISTORY AND ARCHEOLOGY

UDC: 94(4)“01/08”:572.9:903

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.64076/GQP-13.01.2026.023>

Deshko P. P.

Master of Arts in History and Law,
Head of Academic Affairs,
Augustyn Voloshyn Carpathian University
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-8476-6021>

FACTORS AND MECHANISMS OF THE MIGRATION OF THE CELTIC RUTENI IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE

According to the hypothesis proposed here, between the first century BCE and the eighth century CE there were at least two major migration trajectories of the Celtic Ruteni. The first wave moved from Narbonese Gaul to the province of Noricum and from there to the Danube region, the Carpathian foothills, the Black Sea area, and the Dnieper basin. The second followed a route toward the Baltic coast, to the island of Rügen, and later – after the subjugation of the Rugii by the Goths – together with them to the Dnieper region.

As a result of these periodic migration impulses, the Celtic Ruteni entered into long-term contact with the Slavic (proto-Ukrainian) population, becoming involved in the processes that shaped the Ukrainian ethnic community, its collective identity, and the early state formations of Rus’.

The migratory activity of the Celtic Ruteni was determined by a complex of factors. The decisive impulse was the Roman conquest of Gaul by Julius Caesar in 58–50 BCE, which lasted about eight years and ended with the incorporation of Gallic territories into the Roman state. The Celtic Ruteni were characterized by a high level of economic specialization: within their area (southern Gaul, the Central Massif) mining, metallurgy, and trade were well developed, including the extraction of iron and copper ores and gold-bearing alluvial deposits.

The Ruteni participated actively in long-distance transcontinental trade between the Mediterranean and Northern Europe, exchanging metals, salt, amber, wine, and ceramics. An important indicator of their economic autonomy is the fact that they minted their own gold and silver coinage, which was possible only under conditions of stable access to metal resources. Thus, the Celtic Ruteni appear not as a purely military-tribal community but as a complex society with developed extractive industries and trade, typical of La Tène Celtic civilization.

At the same time, Roman incorporation in the first century BCE significantly worsened the socio-economic position of the Ruteni. After the conquest of Gaul, the Roman administration: (1) established control over the mines; (2) destroyed autonomous tribal economic structures; (3) integrated metallurgical production into the system of imperial estates. The consequence was the deprivation of the Celtic elites, including the Ruteni, of economic agency.

A major stimulus to migration was also the transformation of trade routes in the first to third centuries, when Atlantic–continental and intra-Celtic routes declined, while Mediterranean communications under Roman control became dominant. The situation was further aggravated by the crisis of Late Antiquity in the third to fifth centuries, manifested in empire-wide financial and demographic upheavals, the decline of the monetary economy, and a reduction in demand for metals. Archaeologically, these processes are reflected in the disappearance of mining operations and craft centers in Central and Southern Gaul.

One argument in favor of the migration of the Ruteni is the mention in a charter of the East Frankish king Louis the German from 863 of the toponym *Ruzaramarcha* (in the territory of modern Lower and Upper Austria), which indicates the settlement of Celts within the former Noricum and the Danube region. Additional confirmation is provided by Danubian toponyms such as *Rotularius*, *Reodarii*, *Rosdorf*, and *Ruzische Mushel* (*Russenmühle*). Toponymic material from Central and Eastern Europe as a whole supports this hypothesis (see Fig. 1): *Ruzaramarcha*, *Rudotice*, *Rudice*, *Rusovice*, *Ruse*, *Rutenovici*, *Rus'ki Geyivtsi*, *Ruska*, *Rososh*, *Ruzhyn*, *Ros'*, *Rosava*, *Rostavytsia*, and others.

Figure 1. Map of toponyms associated with the ethnonyms “Ruteni,” “Rugii,” and “Rusyns” (Source: compiled by the author).

At the same time, in the fifth century the kingdom of Rugiland – the state of the Rugii – existed in the territory of Lower Austria. It is argued here that the Rugii represent a Germanicized phonetic form of the ethnonym Ruteni. This concerns a process of gutturalization of consonants with the transition of *t* to *d* and later to *g* (*ruti* → *rudi* → *rugi*) [4, p. 49]. As a result of adaptation to the Frankish linguistic environment, the Ruteni became known under the name Rugii. The identity of the Rugii and the Ruteni is also supported by source comparisons: in Julius Caesar, the Ruteni are localized in southern Gaul next to the Lemovices, whereas Tacitus reports the neighborhood of the Baltic Rugii with the Lemovii. This may be regarded as indirect evidence of the migration of the Ruteni to the Baltic coast, which also correlates with toponymy: *Rüg*, *Rugenhof*, *Rugard*, *Rushvitz*, *Rügenwald*.

In turn, V. H. Skliarenko emphasizes that the Celts possessed a developed salt industry, and it is precisely with the Celts that the beginning of salt extraction in the Carpathian region is associated [5, p. 22]. Powerful salt deposits in the area of Halych supplied the needs of the whole of Kyivan Rus'; it is no coincidence that sources record that during the wars of the Kyivan princes with Galicia, a shortage of salt was felt throughout Rus'. Such a level of salt economy may indicate the presence of the Celtic Ruteni in the region.

In addition, Skliarenko connects the ethnonym *rutheni* with the Celtic *roudos* (“red”), drawing attention to the description by Marcus Lucan *flavi rutheni* (“fair/red-haired Ruteni”), as well as to Ibn Fadlan’s report on the fair-haired appearance of the Rus'. In the scholar’s view, this is an additional argument in favor of a connection between the Rus' and the Celtic Ruteni [5, p. 23].

Archaeological materials also record a pronounced Celtic influence on Slavic cultures – from Przeworsk to Chernyakhiv. It is manifested in the forms and ornamentation of pottery (rhombic, zigzag, spiral, and circular motifs), in wheel-made traditions of Celtic origin, and in specific ritual practices, including the custom of bending swords. Important is also the spread of the cremation rite, characteristic of the Ruteni as well as of the Przeworsk and Zarubyntsi cultures; in the Chernyakhiv culture it is observed in combination with inhumation.

From a linguistic perspective, according to the observations of K. M. Tyshchenko, a Celtic component can be traced in the Ukrainian language, in particular in the functioning of the suffix **-yna** and in a distinct lexical layer [6]: *liudyna* (person), *divchyna* (girl), *rodyna* (family), *tvaryna* (animal), *drabyna* (ladder). The scholar also identifies a number of probable Celtic borrowings: *sluha* (servant), *vlada* (power), *liky* (medicine), *bevzen* (fool), *shchyt* (shield), *molytysia* (to pray), *salo* (lard), and others [8, p. 34].

Alongside written, linguistic, and archaeological data, the influence of the Celtic Ruteni can also be traced in the sphere of foreign relations. Thus, the son of Uldin, ruler of the western Hunnic khaganate, bore the

name Rugila (Rua), which may reflect local traditions and possible Celtic naming. Important arguments in favor of the existence of Rus' before 862 and of the migration of the Celtic Ruteni to the Black Sea region and the Dnieper basin are the campaigns of the Rus' against Surozh and Amastris in the eighth to ninth centuries, as well as finds of Celtic Montefortino-type helmets in the Black Sea area.

In addition, the Moravian rulers Rastislav and Sviatopolk I in their titulature identified themselves as princes of Rus', which indirectly confirms the presence of the Celtic Ruteni in the Danube region. Byzantine authors identified the Rus' with Scythians, Tauro-Scythians, and Tauri [5, pp. 17–18], which indicates their long presence in the region, since in medieval tradition ancient ethnonyms were applied to peoples with deep historical continuity.

Thus, the totality of the historical, archaeological, linguistic, and toponymic data presented provides grounds to argue that the Celtic Ruteni migrated to the Danube region and later found themselves in the Dnieper basin, which is supported by the arguments outlined above.

References

1. Deshko P. P. The Celtic Theory of the Origins of Rus' as an Alternative to Normanism and the Concept of the «Old Rus' Ethnicity». *Scientific and Theoretical Almanac «Grani»*. 2025. Vol. 28, No. 4. P. 70–79. <https://doi.org/10.15421/172586>
2. Дешко П. П. Етногенетичні процеси українського народу в історико-культурному вимірі кельтської концепції походження Русі. *Науково-теоретичний альманах «Грані»*. 2025. Т. 28, № 5. С. 240–245. URL: <https://doi.org/10.15421/172624>
3. Дешко П. П. Переосмислення концепції «давньоруської народності» у світлі кельтської теорії походження Русі. *Актуальні проблеми гуманітарних наук*. 2025. Т. 1, № 87. С. 59–69. <https://doi.org/10.24919/2308-4863/87-1-7>
4. Прицак О. Й. Походження Русі. Стародавні скандинавські джерела: в 2 т. / О. Й. Прицак. Київ: Обереги, 1997. Т. 1. 1080 с.
5. Склярєнко В. Г. Походження назви Русь. *Мовознавство*. 2011. № 3. С. 16–25.
6. Тищенко К. М. Десять історичних свідків прадавності української мови. *Вісник НТШ*. 2023. № 67. С. 64–76.
7. Тищенко К. М. Кельтські назви селищ на витоках річок України. *Народна творчість та етнографія*. 2003. № 5-6. С. 63–73.
8. Тищенко К. М. Контури лексико-топонімічної стратиграфії України і етногенез українців. *Народна творчість та етнографія*. 2005. № 4. С. 31–44.
9. Цветков С. Э. Начало русской истории. С древнейших времен до княжения Олега. Москва: ЗАО Центрполиграф, 2012. 429 с. URL: https://www.phantastike.com/history/nachalo_russkoj_istorii_s_drevn_vremen/djvu/view/ (дата звернення: 04.01.2026).